

ICC YOU THERE! REASONS AFFECTING PARENT'S LOYALTY TO IMMACULATE CONCEPTION COLLEGE OF BALAYAN INC.

Russell Lagos¹, Armand Son B. Ramos III², Marklo T. Tamayo³, and Angel Maria H. Esguerra⁴, Jowenie A. Mangarin⁵

Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc.

Corresponding Email: armansonramos@gmail.com

Available Online: March 2025
Revised: January 2025
Accepted: January 2025
Received: February 2025

Volume III Issue 1 (2025)
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15039501
E-ISSN: 2984-7184
P-ISSN: 2984-7176
<https://getinternational.org/research/>

Abstract

This study examines the factors influencing parental loyalty to Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. (ICCBI), with the goal of developing strategic recommendations to strengthen this relationship. Using a qualitative case study design, the researchers explored expressions of loyalty, contributing factors, and strategies for improvement through semi-structured interviews with ten purposively selected parents identified as loyal parents. The findings highlight that loyalty is fostered by ICCBI's commitment to quality Catholic education, affordable tuition, and positive parent-teacher interactions. Expressions of loyalty include continued enrollment, advocacy through word-of-mouth, and active parental involvement in school activities. Challenges, such as maintaining consistent communication and enhancing quality education, were identified as areas for improvement. Key recommendations include the development of a comprehensive promotional plan, enhancement of parental engagement through social media and events, and the implementation of innovative teaching strategies. These insights contribute to ICCBI's strategic goals, providing actionable strategies to enhance parental loyalty and support its mission of delivering transformative education.

Keywords: *Customer loyalty, Customer Satisfaction, Educational services, Loyalty, Service quality*

Recommended Citation:

Lagos, R., Ramos III, A. S. B., Tamayo, M. T., Esguerra, A. M. H., & Mangarin, J. A. (2025). ICC YOU THERE! REASONS AFFECTING PARENT'S LOYALTY TO IMMACULATE CONCEPTION COLLEGE OF BALAYAN INC. GUILD OF EDUCATORS IN TESOL INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH JOURNAL, 3(1), 369–384. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15039501>

INTRODUCTION

The higher education sector has faced unprecedented changes, driven by globalization, digital transformation, and increasing competition. Institutions had to respond to these pressures by adopting market-oriented strategies and delivering measurable value to stakeholders. This included ensuring high-quality education, providing conducive learning environments, and offering sufficient facilities to meet the evolving expectations of parents and students. These determinants significantly influenced loyalty, enrollment decisions, and institutional reputation. In such a competitive arena, only institutions excelling in these areas could achieve sustainable growth and long-term success.

In educational settings, parent loyalty closely mirrored the concept of customer loyalty in the business sector. It was characterized by a strong and enduring commitment to a preferred institution, demonstrated through repeated enrollments and positive advocacy. Research highlighted the critical role of such loyalty in driving a school's success, influencing not only its sustainability but also its capacity for growth. Sao Mai and Tri Cuong (2020) asserted that parental loyalty was a key determinant of institutional stability, especially in the context of heightened competition among schools.

Existing literature provided insights into factors affecting loyalty, yet significant gaps remained in research on parent loyalty in educational contexts, particularly at ICCBI. Studies such as Adefulu et al. (2020) revealed that factors like facilities, geographic location, course availability, and influences from family and peers shaped students' university preferences. Similarly, Debildos and Gatmaitan (2024) found that parents from low- to middle-income families valued private education for its perceived quality but were constrained by affordability and access to subsidies. These findings, while valuable, primarily addressed student preferences and financial considerations, leaving the dynamics of parent loyalty underexplored.

Moreover, Laureta et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of evaluating parental and student satisfaction with school services to maintain and enhance service quality. Such evaluations allowed institutions to identify areas for improvement while highlighting their strengths, providing a critical feedback loop for administrators. Oberfield (2020) further underscored the importance of parental perceptions, suggesting they served as key indicators of institutional performance and academic achievement. Despite these insights, existing research largely focused on student loyalty, underscoring the need to shift attention to parents as equally significant stakeholders in educational success.

Motivated by these gaps, this study examined the factors influencing parent loyalty at ICCBI. "ICC YOU THERE!", ICCBI's hallmark tagline, reflected the institution's commitment to fostering trust and engagement among families. This commitment had become a cornerstone of ICCBI's pursuit of growth and development. Recognizing the vital role of collaborative relationships among families, schools, and the broader community, ICCBI had outlined strategic initiatives aimed at fostering these connections. These initiatives included developmental programs for parents, students, and staff, enhancements to Catholic Education Programs, and the establishment of local and international networks. These efforts sought to improve academic performance and achieve the pastoral goals of the Archdiocese of Lipa, positioning ICCBI as a model institution that upheld both educational excellence and community engagement. Understanding these variables was crucial for identifying actionable strategies to enhance parental trust and engagement. The study's findings contributed to ICCBI's strategic goals, offering evidence-based recommendations for strengthening marketing efforts, enrollment strategies, and overall service quality.

Thus, the objective of this study not only sought to address gaps in existing literature but also provided practical implications for ICCBI and similar institutions. Strengthening relationships with parents and aligning services

with their expectations would enable ICCBI to secure its continued growth and fulfill its mission of providing transformative, Christ-centered education in a rapidly changing world.

Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to explore the factors that influence parents' loyalty to ICCBI, aiming to strengthen the institution's relationship with its stakeholders. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How do parents express their loyalty to ICCBI?
2. What factors influence parents' loyalty to ICCBI?
3. What recommendations do loyal parents provide to foster greater loyalty among other parents?
4. What promotional strategies can effectively enhance parents' loyalty to ICCBI?
5. Based on the findings, what promotional strategy can be recommended to effectively enhance parents' loyalty to ICCBI?

METHODS

This study utilized a qualitative case-study design to explore the factors influencing parental loyalty to Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. (ICCBI), effectively capturing the complex emotions and perceptions driving parental loyalty through rich, detailed insights. The case study method facilitated an in-depth understanding of parental loyalty within its natural context, enabling effective engagement with participants who articulated their motivations and experiences through interviews, revealing the nuanced reasons behind their loyalty. This comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to parental loyalty was essential for developing targeted interventions and strategies to strengthen school-community relations.

POPULATION and SAMPLING

The population for this study consisted of parents of students from Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. (ICCBI) who were recognized for their loyalty during the 2023-2024 graduation rites, selected based on their demonstrated commitment to the institution, providing them with relevant experiences to inform the study on parental loyalty. The researchers employed judgmental sampling to target a specific group of parents who met predefined criteria for loyalty, ensuring that the participants had a deep understanding of ICCBI's services, making them ideal for exploring the factors that influence parental loyalty. A total of ten participants were chosen to balance manageability with the need for diverse perspectives, ensuring a sample that was both representative and rich in relevant insights. The sampling criteria focused on parents who had received a loyalty award and had at least two children who had studied at ICCBI, ensuring that participants had sufficient experience with the institution's services to provide meaningful perspectives. Additionally, to meet the study's eligibility requirements, each participant had to have children who had graduated from at least two different academic levels at ICCBI, these levels included Grade School to Junior High School (JHS) and Senior High School (SHS), or JHS and SHS to College, ensuring that the parents had a comprehensive understanding of ICCBI's educational offerings across multiple departments, further enriching the data collected on the factors influencing parental loyalty.

INSTRUMENTATIONS

To achieve the primary goal of the study, the researchers gathered essential information through semi-structured interviews, which were well-suited for exploring the complex motivations and experiences of parents regarding their loyalty to ICCBI. Specifically, a semi-structured interview format was employed, allowing the researchers to ask predetermined questions while incorporating follow-up questions based on participants' responses. This format enabled a deeper exploration of their insights.

To uncover the reasons behind parental loyalty at ICCBI, the interview questions were designed to address specific study objectives. Objective 1 delved into the factors influencing parental loyalty, including academic programs, school culture, teacher-parent communication, and the school's Catholic identity. Objective 2 explored how parents expressed their loyalty through actions such as word-of-mouth recommendations, volunteering, and participation in school events. Finally, to address Objective 3, parents were asked for specific recommendations on how ICCBI could further foster loyalty among its parent community, potentially revealing areas for improvement or highlighting successful strategies.

DATA COLLECTION

The researchers submitted a formal letter to the college dean requesting approval to conduct the study, ensuring adherence to institutional protocols and ethical considerations in research. The study sought validation of the interview questions from experts in educational research to confirm their relevance and appropriateness for the study's objectives. The researchers prepared written consent from participants through a detailed consent letter, which outlined the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and the participants' rights. The researchers delivered open-ended questions, allowing parents to express their experiences and perceptions freely. Throughout the interview, the researchers actively listened, took detailed notes, or recorded the conversation (with consent) and maintained a respectful, non-judgmental attitude to encourage open and honest communication. After gathering all available data, the researchers transcribed the interviews and categorized the responses thematically. The study adviser then reviewed the compiled data to ensure accuracy and coherence before proceeding with the analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS

Given that thematic analysis focused primarily on identifying shared or common meanings across data, it was less effective for analyzing the unique individual perspectives of each participant. A six step-step framework for conducting thematic analysis in lieu with Kiger and Varpio (2020), which included; Familiarization, where researchers engaged with the data to understand its depth and context; Generating Initial Codes, which involved systematically coding the data to identify meaningful segments; Identifying Patterns, where similar codes were grouped into potential themes; Assessing Patterns, which evaluated the validity and relevance of the identified themes; Defining and Categorizing Patterns, where the themes were refined and their scope defined; and Producing the Final Report, in which the findings were compiled into a coherent report or publication. This method was particularly suitable for the research as it allowed for an in-depth exploration of parents' experiences and motivations, helping to identify themes critical to understanding their loyalty to ICCBI.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

In preparation for the interview, researchers provided participants with a consent form that detailed the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits, ensuring they fully understood the information before giving their

consent. To protect the confidentiality of participants' data, researchers replaced participants' actual names with code names in all study records and reports. These measures addressed key ethical considerations, including: informed consent, ensuring that participants fully understood the study and their rights before agreeing to participate; respect for privacy, safeguarding personal information and restricting its use strictly to research purposes; and minimization of potential risks, taking steps to reduce any discomfort or harm to participants. Furthermore, researchers promoted participants' well-being by providing access to support resources if needed and upheld integrity and transparency by conducting the research honestly, sharing findings responsibly, and maintaining openness throughout the process.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

The analysis and interpretation of data gathered from the answer to the questionnaires distributed. The said data were presented in tabular form in accordance with the specific questions posited on the statement of the problem.

Theme 1: Expressions of school

The findings revealed strong parental loyalty toward ICCBI, driven by trust in its educational quality and nurturing environment. Parents showed this loyalty through consistent enrollment, participation in school events, and advocacy within their community. These actions highlighted their view of ICCBI as a partner in their children's development and their commitment to a community aligned with their values. This loyalty enhanced ICCBI's reputation and strengthened its supportive network. These expressions are categorized into three sub-themes:

1. Continuous Patronage (Participants 1, 3, 4, and 10)
2. Parental Involvement (Participants 1, 5, and 6)
3. Word-of-mouth advocacy (Participants 5 and 8)

Sub-theme 1: Continuous patronage

The sub-theme continues patronage demonstrated by enrolling multiple children or extending education over years, powerfully testifies to parental commitment and a close family-organization relationship, showcasing a strong belief in ICCBI's ability to provide an outstanding and supportive educational experience. Many participants express their loyalty to ICCBI by continuously enrolling their children in the institution. For instance, (P1) "lahat ng mga anak ko ay sa ICCBI ko pinag-aral," while (P3) mentioned, "dito ko pinagtapos ang akin dalawang anak." And (P10) also mentioned that "dito nakapagtapos ang aking apat na anak". This repeated patronage is a clear demonstration of trust in the school's ability to provide quality education over an extended period. Some participants, like (P4), even highlight personal connections with the school, stating, "dito din ako nag-aral noong high school." Loyal, satisfied students who receive high-quality services are more likely to recommend and re-enroll (Rehmana et al., 2020) Creating strong multigenerational bonds and reinforcing long-term loyalty, as evidenced by ICCBI's repeated parental enrollment, which highlights close emotional and social connections rooted in community, faith in quality education, and a desire to share fulfilling experiences across generations.

Sub-theme 2: Parental Involvement

Enhancing communication with parents is a vital strategy for fostering loyalty within the ICCBI community, as it builds trust, encourages involvement, and ensures parents feel valued and informed. Active participation, like attending meetings, orientations, and school activities, strengthens the school-community bond, as seen in P1 dedication: "Sinusuportahan ko ang mga anak ko pag may activities sa ICCBI at palagi rin akong na attend pag may parent meeting

o orientation" ("I support my children in their activities at ICCBI and attend every parent meeting or orientation"). This reflects Erdener and Knoepfel's (2018) findings on the significance of parent-student interactions, academic encouragement, and school-wide communication. P5 support of their child's competitions and P6 sharing of school announcements on social media further highlight how parents remain involved despite busy schedules, creating a positive, supportive atmosphere that strengthens the school-family relationship and fosters a strong sense of community and loyalty.

Sub-theme 3: Word-of-mouth advocacy

The sub-theme of word-of-mouth advocacy highlights parental involvement and loyalty, particularly through parents encouraging others to join ICCBI. P5 emphasized the proactive role parents play in influencing others' decisions about the school, stating, "sa pamamagitan ng paghikayat sa iba pang mga magulang na dito pag-aralin ang kanilang mga anak." This type of promotion reflects strong commitment to the school and serves as an effective means of fostering community and increasing enrollment, aligning with Brown's (2019) findings on the use of promotional techniques in private schools. Word-of-mouth advocacy, driven by parents' positive experiences, strengthens the school's reputation, as parents like P8, who said, "alam ko na secure ang aking anak dito sa school na ito," express trust in the institution's safe, nurturing, and academically sound environment. This type of advocacy not only demonstrates parental loyalty but also plays a crucial role in shaping the school's image and fostering a sense of community.

Theme 2: Reasons for school loyalty

The data reveals several key factors that contribute to the strong sense of loyalty parents feel toward ICCBI. These factors include:

1. Quality Catholic Education (Participants 3, 4, and 5)
2. Positive Interactions with Teachers and Staff (Participants 1 and 5)
3. Accessibility and Affordability (Participants 5, 7, and 9)

Each of these illustrates distinct manifestations of loyalty within a school environment.

Sub-theme 1: Quality Catholic Education

The theme of providing quality Catholic education is a key factor influencing parents' loyalty to ICCBI, as emphasized by P3, 4, and 5. Their testimonies highlight the importance of high-quality education in building trust and fostering a strong connection with the school. P3 noted, "Nagsisilbing inspirasyon ang mga honors ng mga anak ko. Ang mga achievements nila ay patunay na ang kalidad ng edukasyon ay mataas dito" ("My children's honors serve as an inspiration. Their achievements are proof that the quality of education here is high"), while P4 highlighted the curriculum's balanced focus on academics and character development: "Ang curriculum dito ay hindi lang nakatuon sa academics kundi pati na rin sa character development. Ito ang dahilan kung bakit umaasa ako na makakabuti ang ICCBI para sa aking anak" ("The curriculum here focuses not only on academics but also on character development. This is why I believe ICCBI will benefit my child"). These insights align with Meier and Lemmer's (2018) research on parents valuing high academic standards, effective instruction, school discipline, and student safety. ICCBI's Catholic education program promotes holistic development by emphasizing values such as self-discipline, faith, and accountability, with P5 explaining, "Ang mga misa at mga retreat ay nagbibigay ng pagkakataon sa mga bata na

mapalalim ang kanilang pananampalataya. Ang mga ito ay hindi lang mga aktibidad kundi bahagi ng kanilang paghubog" ("The Masses and retreats offer children opportunities to deepen their faith. These are not just activities but part of their formation"). The school's commitment to both academic excellence and religious formation strengthens the bond with families, particularly those who prioritize faith-based education, reinforcing ICCBI's role as a trusted educational partner for families.

Sub-theme 2: Positive Interactions with Teachers and Staff

The theme of Community and Relationship with Staff emerged from the insights of P1, 5, and , highlighting the significant impact of relationships within the ICCBI community on parents' loyalty to the school. Positive interactions with school personnel, including teachers and non-teaching staff, were especially appreciated. P1 shared, "mas naging buo ang loob ko na sa iccbi paralin ang mga anak ko dahil ang babait ng mga school teachers pati na rin ang mga non-teaching staff," which reflects how these relationships reinforce trust in the institution. Eldegwy's (2022) research supports this, noting that parents' perceptions of faculty, staff, and the school environment affect their satisfaction. Additionally, regular communication and involvement in school activities allowed parents like P5 to build deeper relationships with teachers, as they stated, "Ang mga guro ay laging handang makinig at tumulong. Kaya't ramdam namin na may kaagapay kami sa pag-aalaga sa aming mga anak" ("The teachers are always ready to listen and help. We feel that we have support in caring for our children"). This openness and approachability foster a nurturing environment where parents feel valued and engaged, strengthening their loyalty to the school and its community.

Sub-theme 3: Accessibility and Affordability

The theme of Accessibility and Affordability is crucial in influencing parents' loyalty to ICCBI, as highlighted by P5, 7, and 9. Accessibility plays a vital role, with P5 and 7 sharing, "Ang accessibility ng paaralan ay talagang malaking bagay. May mga oras na kailangan ko ng makausap ang guro, at madali lang ako makapunta sa ICCBI." ("The school's accessibility is really significant. There are times when I need to talk to the teacher, and I can easily go to ICCBI"), underscoring how the school's proximity facilitates communication and strengthens their connection to the school. Additionally, affordability is a key factor, with P9 sharing, "Nakatanggap kami ng scholarship, at ito ay nagbigay ng malaking ginhawa sa aming pamilya. Dahil dito, mas nakatuon ako sa pag-aaral ng aking mga anak" ("We received a scholarship, and this provided great relief for our family. Because of this, I can focus more on my children's studies"). This aligns with Hartani et al. (2019), who noted that parents consider educational expenses, quality, and reputation when choosing schools. ICCBI's reasonable tuition fees, along with scholarships and flexible payment options, make it accessible for families from various socioeconomic backgrounds. P7 also appreciated the affordability of supporting two children at the same time. The combination of accessible and affordable education allows families to prioritize their children's education without significant financial strain, fostering their loyalty to the institution.

Theme 3: Recommended ways to improve school loyalty

The data from participants highlights several key strategies to strengthen parental loyalty toward ICCBI. The recommendations focus on

1. Improving the quality of education (Participants 2, 6, and 8)
2. Increasing parental involvement (Participants 5, 6, 7, 9,)
3. Providing orientation for new parents (Participants 1, 3, 4, and 7)

Each of these elements contributes to building a stronger relationship between the school and its community, fostering long-term commitment from families.

Sub-theme 1: Improving the quality of education

The theme of improving the quality of education emerged as a significant factor in fostering parent loyalty at ICCBI, as parents emphasized the importance of an outstanding educational experience in assessing the school's value. Participant 6 highlighted, "if you have high-quality education, you don't need to do promotional ads," suggesting that parents will naturally recommend the school based on its academic excellence. P2 echoed this by stressing the need for continuous improvements to ensure students are fully prepared for the future. Enhancing classroom infrastructure, like better ventilation as mentioned by P8, could further improve the learning environment and boost parent satisfaction. Cheng et al. (2020) also noted that innovations in service delivery increase loyalty through positive experiences. Parents strongly advocate for improvements in teacher training, showcasing student accomplishments, ensuring the curriculum is relevant, and providing adequate resources, all of which contribute to a stronger reputation and higher parent loyalty.

Sub-theme 2: Increasing parental involvement

Increasing parental involvement was widely suggested as a way to boost school loyalty, with parents emphasizing the importance of regular communication and active participation in school activities to strengthen the connection between the school and its community. P9 highlighted the need for "more communication with the parents and teachers" to allow for greater parental contribution to their children's learning and well-being. Regular engagement through Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) meetings, as suggested by P6 and 7, and family-oriented events like Family Day, recommended by P9, would help foster a sense of community and belonging. Sirilis et al. (2021) also noted that parental involvement positively impacts student academic outcomes and increases customer loyalty, which are both essential for the school's sustainability. Additionally, many parents, including P1, advocated for more frequent use of social media to keep parents informed and engaged by showcasing the school's successes and student achievements. To further enhance involvement and loyalty, P6 emphasized the value of word-of-mouth advertising, which could be amplified by an active social media presence. Holding regular meetings to update parents on school projects, as suggested by P3 and 4, would also contribute to building a stronger, more loyal parent base. Ultimately, promoting parental involvement through open communication, engagement opportunities, and a supportive atmosphere is key to enhancing parent loyalty at ICCBI.

Sub-theme 3: Providing orientation for new parents

The theme of providing orientation for new parents is seen as a key recommendation for fostering loyalty at ICCBI, with participants emphasizing the importance of open communication about school policies, academic progress, and organizational changes. P3 and 4 suggested holding orientations that clearly outline the school's programs, strengths, and values, helping parents understand the benefits their children will receive, as noted by P1, who highlighted the need to "explain the benefits their children will receive while attending the school." Many parents also value learning about the school's affordability, financial aid, and scholarship options during these orientations. Regular follow-up

meetings throughout the school year, as recommended by P7, would further maintain transparency and engagement, making new families feel welcomed. By providing orientation, encouraging collaboration with the administration, and offering timely updates on academic success, school regulations, and organizational changes, ICCBI can strengthen its support system, enhance communication, and build stronger relationships between parents and the school.

Theme 4: Impressions on specific promotional strategies

The data gathered from parents reveals their perspectives on several promotional strategies used by ICCBI to strengthen loyalty and attract new families. These strategies include

1. Active Engagement on Social Media Page (Participants 1, 6 and 7)
2. Discounts and scholarships (Participants 7 and 9)
3. Alumni testimonials (Participants 1, 7, and 9)

Which collectively help enhance the school's reputation and engagement with both existing and prospective parents.

Sub-theme 1: Active Engagement on Social Media Page

The theme of active engagement on social media is a vital expression of parental loyalty to ICCBI, as digital platforms serve as essential tools for fostering community, communication, and involvement. Many parents view the school's social media pages as a valuable resource for staying updated on events, activities, and programs. P1 noted, "mas nagiging updated kami sa kung ano man ang mga activities or events na gaganapin sa school," reflecting the importance of real-time access to information. P7 also highlighted how it "napapadali nito ang access sa paaralan," making it easier for parents to stay informed. Smith (2017) emphasizes that effective marketing strategies, including social media, impact student enrollment, retention rates, and public opinion, helping to build transparency and connection, thus increasing parental loyalty. However, some participants, like P6, suggested improving the organization of posts or consolidating the multiple Facebook pages for different departments to make it easier for parents to follow updates. Overall, the use of social media helps foster a sense of belonging, emotional connection, and open communication, all of which play a significant role in promoting parental loyalty at ICCBI.

Sub-theme 2: Discounts and scholarships

The theme of offering discounts and promotions is a significant indicator of parental loyalty at ICCBI, highlighting the importance of financial considerations in both the initial decision to enroll and ongoing commitment to the school. Participants consistently identified discounts as a crucial factor in making education more financially accessible. For instance, P7 noted, "malaking tulong ang mga discount na binibigay ng ICCBI at ito ay nakahihikayat sa mga magulang," emphasizing how these financial incentives alleviate the burden of rising tuition fees. Behaunek et al.

(2019) also noted that many private universities use discounts to attract students who may struggle to pay full tuition, further supporting the idea that affordability plays a key role in both attracting and retaining families. P9, a single parent, mentioned how ICCBI's "barkada promo, ESC, and alumni promo" were crucial in supporting their child's education, reflecting the significant role financial help plays in fostering loyalty. Ultimately, trust in the school's understanding of families' financial struggles, the benefits of promotions, and emotional connections created through shared experiences form the foundation of this commitment.

Sub-theme 3: Alumni testimonials

The theme of alumni testimonials is a compelling indicator of parental loyalty to ICCBI, as positive experiences from former students reinforce trust and commitment among current families. Participants highlighted how alumni success stories validate the quality of education and foster pride and connection to the school community. P1 noted, "mas maraming tao ang gugustuhin na pumasok sa ICCBI pag nalaman nila na nakatulong ang school sa success na nakamit nila sa buhay nila," illustrating how parents find encouragement in these success stories, emphasizing the long-term positive effects of an ICCBI education. P7 further emphasized that alumni testimonials offer concrete evidence of the school's impact, while notable alumni like Hon. Eduardo Ermita, as mentioned by P9, add credibility and enhance the school's reputation. These success stories not only serve as powerful testimonials but also strengthen community relationships, inspire current families, and create emotional bonds, ultimately fostering loyalty.

CONCLUSION

The results indicated that parental loyalty to ICCBI was cultivated through continuous engagement, trust, and robust community connections. Parents consistently selected ICCBI for their children's education, with their loyalty strengthened by active participation in school events and community advocacy. This support demonstrated their confidence in the institution's capacity to deliver high-quality education, which in turn bolstered its reputation and contributed to its growth. Parental trust and involvement were essential factors in ICCBI's success.

The study emphasized that parental loyalty to ICCBI was influenced by several critical factors: the institution's dedication to providing quality Catholic education, strong relationships within the community and with staff, and its accessibility and affordability. Parents expressed strong loyalty to ICCBI due to its holistic approach that integrates academic excellence with moral and spiritual development, which aligns with their values. Positive interactions with teachers, staff, and fellow families fostered a sense of belonging, contributing to a supportive environment. Additionally, the school's accessibility and affordable tuition made it an appealing choice for families, ensuring that financial limitations did not hinder their ability to prioritize quality education. These elements enhanced ICCBI's reputation and reinforced parental loyalty.

The findings of this study suggest that ICCBI's capacity to cultivate parental loyalty is grounded in several essential areas. Parents' dedication to their children's education highlights the significance of ongoing enhancements

in educational quality, such as academic excellence, innovative teaching strategies, and comprehensive programs. Strengthening parental involvement is critical to developing a more robust relationship between parents and the school. Consistent communication, participation in events like Family Day, and an active presence on social media help keep parents informed and engaged. Furthermore, effective orientation programs for new parents are crucial in building trust and fostering long-term commitment by ensuring transparent communication regarding school policies, academic progress, and available financial support.

The findings of this study identify several key factors that significantly contribute to parental loyalty to ICCBI. Active engagement on social media is essential for enhancing communication and transparency, as it helps build a sense of community and belonging. Social media platforms are crucial tools for keeping parents updated and connected to school activities. Moreover, the provision of discounts, promotions, and scholarships plays an important role in reinforcing parental loyalty by addressing financial concerns and improving access to education. These financial incentives not only attract new families but also help retain existing ones. Additionally, alumni testimonials strengthen parental trust by highlighting the long-term benefits and success stories associated with an ICCBI education, thereby increasing confidence in the school's quality and fostering a sense of pride among parents.

REFERENCES

- Adefulu, A., Farinloye, T., & Mogaji, E. (2020). Factors influencing postgraduate students' university choice in Nigeria. In *Springer eBooks* (pp. 187–225). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-39379-3_8
- Alam, M. M. (2022). SEM Model to analyze the factors affecting university image: A study on International Islamic University Chittagong. *Dirāsāt Al-ġāmī'at Al-islāmiyyat Al-'ālamīyyat Šītāġūng*, 18(1), 65–88. <https://doi.org/10.3329/iiucs.v18i1.61275>
- An analysis on the influence of tuition and service quality on parents' satisfaction and its effect on their loyalty at TK Swasta Sriwijaya, Medan.* (2019). https://www.ijrrjournal.com/IJRR_Vol.6_Issue.7_July2019/Abstract_IJRR0050.html
- Annamdevula, S., & Bellamkonda, R. S. (2016). Effect of student perceived service quality on student satisfaction, loyalty and motivation in Indian universities. *Journal of Modelling in Management*, 11(2), 488–517. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jm2-01-2014-0010>
- Arigata, I. M. D., Anggraini, N. P. N., & Ribek, P. K. (n.d.). *The Effect of Service Quality, Price Perception and Trust on Parents Satisfaction at Kartika Mandala Kindergarten in Denpasar.* International Journal of Tourism and Hospitality in Asia Pasific. <https://doi.org/10.32535/ijthap.v5i1.1412>

ASSESSMENT OF PARENTS AND TEACHERS SATISFACTION IN PRIVATE SCHOOL: THE CASE OF SOLIANA ACADEMY

- S.C. (2018). (n.d.).
- Bartik, T. J., Hershbein, B., & Lachowska, M. (2016). The Merits of Universal Scholarships: Benefit-Cost Evidence from the Kalamazoo Promise. *Journal of Benefit-Cost Analysis*, 7(3), 400–433. <https://doi.org/10.1017/bca.2016.22>
- Behaunek, L., & Gansemer-Topf, A. M. (2019). Tuition discounting at small, private, baccalaureate institutions: reaching a point of no return? *Journal of Student Financial Aid*, 48(3). <https://doi.org/10.55504/0884-9153.1645>
- Blake, B., & Mestry, R. (2021). The influence of parental demographics on school choice decision-making in Western Gauteng, South Africa. *South African Journal of Education*, 41(3), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.15700/saje.v41n3a1958>
- Cash, T. N., & Oppenheimer, D. M. (2024). Parental rights or parental wrongs: Parents' metacognitive knowledge of the factors that influence their school choice decisions. *PloS One*, 19(4), e0301768. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0301768>
- Chairunnisa, C. C. (2018a). The effect of brand image and quality of educational services on customer satisfaction. *Jurnal Manajemen - Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Tarumanagara/Jurnal Manajemen*, 22(3), 325. <https://doi.org/10.24912/jm.v22i3.425>
- Chairunnisa, C. C. (2018b). The effect of brand image and quality of educational services on customer satisfaction. *Jurnal Manajemen - Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Tarumanagara/Jurnal Manajemen*, 22(3), 325. <https://doi.org/10.24912/jm.v22i3.425>
- Cheng, B. L., Cham, T. H., Dent, M. M., & Lee, T. H. (2019). Service innovation: building a sustainable competitive advantage in higher education. *International Journal of Services, Economics and Management*, 10(4), 289. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijsem.2019.105014>
- Clark, E. (2021). The role of digital marketing in higher education. *Journal of Higher Education Management*, 36(3), 211-228.
- White, C. (2022). The impact of social media marketing on higher education institutions. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 45(1), 67-82. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378948410_Exploring_Promotional_Strategies_in_Private_Universities_A_Comprehensive_Analysis_of_Tactics_and_Innovative_Approaches#full-text
- Eldegwy, A., Elsharnouby, T. H., & Kortam, W. (2022). Like father like son: the role of similar-education parents in their children's university choice. *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08841241.2021.2018087>

- Ellison, S., & Aloe, A. M. (2018). Strategic Thinkers and Positioned Choices: Parental decision making in urban school choice. *Educational Policy*, 33(7), 1135–1170. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904818755470>
- Enhancement of educational services by using the internet of things applications for talent and intelligent schools.* (2020). <http://pen.ius.edu.ba/index.php/pen/article/view/1744>
- Factors influencing customer satisfaction and loyalty of online educational platform in Indonesia: Analysis of E-Service Quality Factors.* (2021). <https://rb.gy/lmuwfi>
- History of ICC – Immaculate Conception College – Balayan, Batangas.* (n.d.). https://iccbalayan.edu.ph/history-of-icc/?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMTEAAR2JKnY5RL6bewrj2TCHe1AU-eNpkWD8LLmHMB2CiQVVqriTXE0coXHde0_aem_Sgs5QXmMHLbIT2pg9A2K6g
- How can schools support parents' engagement in their children's learning? Evidence from research and practice.* (2017). https://ore.exeter.ac.uk/repository/bitstream/handle/10871/39347/Parental_Engagement_-_Evidence_from_Research_and_Practice.pdf?sequence=1
- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378899149_ANALYZING_THE_IMPACT_OF_DIGITAL_MARKETING_AND_PROMOTIONAL_STRATEGIES_ON_ADMISSION_PREFERENCES_IN_PRIVATE_UNIVERSITIES
- Kim, J. (2017). The impact of different price promotions on customer retention. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 46, 95–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2017.10.007>
- Justin, L. D., Jin, S., & Hubert, V. (2019b). Effect of international students' perceived service quality on the student's motivation, satisfaction, loyalty, and institutional image in higher education in China. *Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2587994>
- Kuupiel, C. M., Nangwele, L. D., & Pufaa, N. K. (2024). SCHOOL CHOICE: WHY PARENTS PREFER PRIVATE BASIC SCHOOLS FOR THE EDUCATION OF THEIR WARDS IN NANDOM. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378847415_SCHOOL_CHOICE_WHY_PARENTS_PREFER_PRIVATE_BASIC_SCHOOLS_FOR_THE_EDUCATION_OF_THEIR_WARDS_IN_NANDOM
- Laureta, A. L. N., & Dioso, D. P. D. (2020). Satisfaction of students and parents on school services of Catholic schools in Southern Antique. *Philippine Social Science Journal (University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos-Online)/Philippine Social Science Journal (University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos-Print)*, 3(2), 49–50. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v3i2.229>
- Lewandowska, H. (2024). Parents' expectations of a Student with Special Educational Needs (SEN) regarding the competencies of the educator during the period of contemporary educational transformations. In *Care for a*

- pupil as the essence of the educational process Meeting the omnipotent needs of the pupil (pp. 86-96).* (pp. 86–96). <https://doi.org/10.13166/awsge/187753>
- Meier, C., & Lemmer, E. (2018). Parents as consumers: a case study of parent satisfaction with the quality of schooling. *Educational Review*, 71(5), 617–630. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2018.1465395>
- Mulyono, H., Hadian, A., Purba, N., & Pramono, R. (2020). Effect of service quality toward student satisfaction and loyalty in higher education. *the Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business/the Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(10), 929–938. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no10.929>
- Nguyen, D. T., Pham, V. T., Tran, D. M., & Pham, D. B. T. (2020). Impact of service quality, customer satisfaction and switching costs on customer loyalty. *the Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business/the Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(8), 395–405. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no8.395>
- Nguyen, T., Cao, T. Q., Phung, H. T. T., Nguyen, T. T., Phan, T. T. T., & Pham, H. H. (2022). Parents as customers: The influence of school reputation on satisfaction, feedback, and loyalty of Vietnamese secondary students' parents. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 26(3), 167–178. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41299-022-00144-w>
- Nuphanudin, N., Komariah, A., Kurniady, D. A., Putri, N. S. R., Azzahra, O. R., & Sirilis, N. (2021). Parents in the quality culture. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research/Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210212.001>
- Oberfield, Z. W. (2019). Parent engagement and satisfaction in public charter and district schools. *American Educational Research Journal*, 57(3), 1083–1124. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831219868983>
- Osman, A. R., & Saputra, R. S. (2019). A pragmatic model of student satisfaction: a viewpoint of private higher education. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 27(2), 142–165. <https://doi.org/10.1108/qaе-05-2017-0019>
- Rahman, A. U., Manzoor, W., Yasmin, N., Yaqub, R. M. S., & Ali, M. S. (2024). From service quality to brand loyalty: The mediating effect of student satisfaction in public sector universities. *Pakistan Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.52131/pjhss.2024.v12i2.2215>
- Rehman, M. A., Woyo, E., Akahome, J. E., & Sohail, M. D. (2020a). The influence of course experience, satisfaction, and loyalty on students' word-of-mouth and re-enrolment intentions. *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 32(2), 259–277. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08841241.2020.1852469>
- Relationships between Service Quality, Brand Image, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty.* (n.d.). Retrieved June 12, 2024, from <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no3.0585>

Rosali, L. J., Debildos, J., & Gatmaitan, E. (2024). Parents preference and willingness to pay for private senior high school education. *Journal of Management and Business Education*, 7(1), 137–154.
<https://doi.org/10.35564/jmbe.2024.0008>

Service quality in private secondary schools: extension to EduQUAL with a case from Turkey. (n.d.).
<https://www.berjournal.com/wp-content/plugins/downloads-manager/upload/BERJ12121Article9p.145-155.pdf>

Siegel, A., Esqueda, M., Berkowitz, R., Sullivan, K., Astor, R. A., & Benbenishty, R. (2018). Welcoming Parents to their child's School: practices supporting students with diverse needs and backgrounds. *Education and Urban Society*, 51(6), 756–784. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013124517747682>

The effect of academic service quality on satisfaction and loyalty of students university. (2020a). *Jurnal Ecodemica*, Vol. 4 No. 2 September 2020. https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/75849300/pdf-libre.pdf?1638864147=&response-content-disposition=inline%3B+filename%3DThe_Effect_Of_Academic_Service_Quality_O.pdf&Expires=1718208686&Signature=eeQvo2amVEVPJ2xcAoDemRWjiR4cdOwI0E2sjeG-PXFBA54H1egI440BPGX7bYSSgqEwTfhLZvyjfRUyc2jf9WtUuurSE1VbTyZs9qOcF~BqwK~DengeL3bs08ta0s5HRGaunncgpEQs8MnVfhuMjw2RB-933fYte7ExOfWDRd-7YPD~YYGTBONO9joGYXIZa3NpeWzMrYUPMPy9Y8OFaDeK71y~7v7vsmL5pKxArAIdDt-BHYDnrkYYH2S30MTc7SBgjVUJF9pTVagBWfIwvgEP3b5IuQuqEfbz~86ZkfA8y~kUPI8FOCumwkk3q0Bf64xLghUNa0MamW1CNUPeA_&Key-Pair-Id=APKAJLOHF5GGSLRBV4ZA

The effect of academic service quality on satisfaction and loyalty of students university. (2020b). *Jurnal Ecodemica*, Vol. 4(NO. 2). https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/75849300/pdf-libre.pdf?1638864147=&response-content-disposition=inline%3B+filename%3DThe_Effect_Of_Academic_Service_Quality_O.pdf&Expires=1718121297&Signature=KtQFM9R2Azz8up8ostTxoBWOAVCKf83qeRZhRiFT8QbsqP9Qw4pQasdAqnFjiW2oxr00xVZRHZmP2ZthzHREFD~NDzqmTZFnkOd6-EQ9AJ62pm8ADPOCFAqOAMXMWqorznbKlteIhAnX6DVuyTG7noaaBg8Yx01mYNSC7QrsdoGwDbmJ9XvsJVB92dKhRdIYfycY3IfI6Wt2xczerjmiquVcZ71Jl~m9woelJsmZxy7G9C94B-Y9FK9YGqUHWpV1IAc2viSwq~Nd7ErVlqBjCd6BqtpxFbYrhQxy2BEXkERVOWzq-ijI-fGmTBEIxEUT7aCRf5n7AWAwEhxpBjzg_&Key-Pair-Id=APKAJLOHF5GGSLRBV4ZA

The effect of service quality on satisfaction and loyalty of PAUD student parents. (2021).

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348916322> *The Effect Of Service Quality On Satisfaction And Loyalty Of Paud Student Parents*

Verma, Charul & Jain, Vipin. (2024). ANALYZING THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL MARKETING AND PROMOTIONAL STRATEGIES ON ADMISSION PREFERENCES IN PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES. 98. 58-69.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378899149> *ANALYZING THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL MARKETING AND PROMOTIONAL STRATEGIES ON ADMISSION PREFERENCES IN PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES? tp=eyJjb250ZXh0Ijp7ImZpcnN0UGFnZSI6Il9kaXJlY3QiLCJwYWdlIjojX2RpcmVjdCJ9fQ*

Wei, F., & Ni, Y. (2020). Parent councils, parent involvement, and parent satisfaction: Evidence from rural schools in China. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 51(1), 198–218.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143220968166>

Yusof, N., Zaini, B. J., & Mansor, R. (2019). A study on factors influencing student loyalty towards higher learning institution. *AIP Conference Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5121037>